

A Descriptive-Exploratory Study on Green Logistics Practices and Supply Chain Efficiency for Automotive Businesses in Valenzuela City

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Date Submitted:
June 09, 2026

Date Accepted:
June 09, 2026

Date Published:
June 09, 2026

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.20614771

ABSTRACT

In our modern world, there is a global shift to increase greener practices and sustainable development. This, in turn, impacts firms who need to comply with ever-increasing regulations and environmental concerns. However, current research fails to identify the effects of green logistics practices on the local automotive landscape. The paper aims to understand how green logistics practices — reverse logistics, sustainable use of components, route optimization, localized eco-friendly sourcing, and optimized space allocation — affect the operations of auto manufacturing companies in Valenzuela, discerning their true influence on supply chain efficiency in the region and adding valuable insights to current research. This study is crucial as it offers detailed insights regarding

the impact of sustainable practices on the efficiency of the value chain. A descriptive-exploratory research design was employed. Furthermore, statistical treatment in the form of descriptive statistical methods such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used. Through the usage of survey questionnaires, the study garnered responses from a total of 6 combined managerial employees and officers of automotive firms within Valenzuela City. Using data analysis methods, results showed that green logistics practices had a high impact on supply chain efficiency. Results also implied that green logistics practices helped reduce costs while improving operational performance. With minimal variations, a majority of the respondents agreed that there are numerous advantages and benefits of implementing such practices within the automotive industry. The paper serves as a catalyst for growth, promoting the adoption of such practices locally and aiding future research.

Keywords: *Green logistics practices, logistics, supply chain, operations, efficiency, supply chain efficiency, reverse logistics, sustainable use of components, route optimization, localized eco-friendly sourcing, optimized space allocation*

INTRODUCTION

Earth's warming climate necessitates adaptation. As the world grapples with the effects of climate change, firms must look for cleaner, more sustainable ways to operate. In the 1990s, pressure from both

consumers and stakeholders caused a new set of sustainable practices to emerge (Hariyani, D., Hariyani, P., Mishra, & Sharma, 2024). This helped set the scene for the emergence of green supply chain management (GSCM), under which practices such as green procurement, eco-design, and reverse logistics helped firms innovate and reduce their environmental impact.

In light of global warming, there is a global shift to increase greener practices and sustainable development. In a study by Guzman, Carrillo, & Castro (2021), government authorities have implemented more stringent environmental regulations to reduce pollution on the environment. This, in turn, affects the automotive industry as they contribute a significant amount to pollution. In the year 2022 alone, global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from cars and vans reached 3.53 billion metric tons (GtCO₂) (Tiseo, 2025). As a result, companies are incentivized to explore greener solutions and reduce pollution in their supply chains. Be that as it may, questions arise as to its overall effect on business performance.

A study by Hernandez, Escolano, Juanatas, and Elvambuena (2022) took a closer look into the importance of green logistics practices in Philippine SMEs. The study found that green logistics practices (GLPs) such as route optimization, warehousing sharing, reverse logistics of spare parts, and stepwise electrification of delivery trucks reduced expenditure and increased delivery reliability. Nonetheless, the challenge being tackled by the researchers is identifying the impact of green logistics practices on supply chain efficiency of automotive companies. Even though green practices may bring positive effects on the environment, the business primarily operates to make a profit. Thus, the research seeks to explain concisely the correlation between green logistics and supply chain efficiency.

The paper aims to understand how green logistics practices affect the operations of auto manufacturing companies in Valenzuela, discerning their true impact on supply chain efficiency in the region and adding valuable insights to current research. Current literature fails to examine the local automotive industry, specifically in Valenzuela City. The researchers wanted to conduct the study to provide detailed information which could be utilized by relevant stakeholders and improve the adoption of green logistics by automotive companies within the region.

This study is crucial to automobile companies, specifically those in Valenzuela City because it aims to provide explicit information about the impact of green logistics practices on the efficiency of the supply chain. The research may act as a reference for business operators and managers in order to embrace sustainable practices and enhance everyday operations without compromising competitiveness in the local market. This study aims to provide definitive statistics on sustainable logistics to the academic community, with particular emphasis on automotive firms in Valenzuela City. Municipal authorities can utilize the results as a guideline for designing programs or incentives that induce companies to implement green logistics, both to the advantage of the sector and society as a whole.

METHODS

Research Design

The researchers utilized the descriptive-exploratory design to assess how green logistics practices affect the efficiency of the supply chain. According to a study by Saka, Osademe, and Ononokpono (2023), an exploratory research design aims to explore the research topic in varying depths, serving as a precursor to deeper, more specific study. In this regard, exploratory research is aided by descriptive research to perform a systematic investigation of the research topic. Descriptive research aims to observe, providing a natural view of a group's characteristics (Shinija, N., 2024). Through the application of descriptive research, the researchers may identify underlying trends and formulate accurate descriptions of the variables under study.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted in Valenzuela City, a highly urbanized city located in the northern part of Metro Manila, Philippines. To be specific, the researchers will conduct the study among local automotive

dealers established in Polo, Valenzuela. Polo is a former municipality within Valenzuela City, located in Valenzuela's northern region. Notable automotive companies found include Isuzu Philippines, Mitsubishi Motors Philippines, Toyota Motor Philippines, GAC Motor Philippines, Nissan Motors, Honda Motors, and Yamaha Motors. The chosen city has been awarded for its business friendly environment, implementing the Paspas Permit for seamless business registration and an online V-Link platform aimed at connecting local entrepreneurs with one another (City Government of Valenzuela, 2025). In addition, Valenzuela City is noted for its well developed infrastructure and proximity to major transportation routes such as the North Luzon Expressway (NLEX) and MacArthur highway, strengthening local economic development. As such, Valenzuela City houses a growing number of automotive dealerships, parts suppliers, and logistics providers. The researchers aim to study how these firms make use of green logistics practices and how it impacts supply chain efficiency.

Sampling Technique

The target population for this study consists of managers employed in automotive companies. This specification was made to ensure that the participants must have the expertise needed to provide valid and robust insights into day to day operations and management practices for the local automotive industry. The managers with years of experience must be directly involved in decision making processes, strategic planning and organizational leadership, which makes their perspective important in understanding challenges and opportunities faced by automotive businesses. With years of experience, such respondents have accumulated enough exposure to industry trends, customer demands and regulatory changes, allowing them to provide an exact perspective focusing specifically on the established locale. By clearly defining the respondent pool to managers of automotive companies, the researchers enhance the credibility and deepness of the study, as the data collected is based on professional expertise and long-term industry involvement. A consensus approach was utilized to ensure that all individuals who met the inclusion criteria were considered eligible participants.

To refine participant selection, the study employed purposive (judgmental) sampling, a non-probability technique in which respondents are deliberately selected based on their relevant expertise, knowledge, and experience (Campbell et al., 2020). In this study, purposive sampling enabled the selection of managers with substantial years of experience in the automotive sector, ensuring that participants could provide accurate, contextually grounded insights into managerial practices, operational challenges, and organizational performance. By selecting managers with relevant industry experience, the study ensured that the data collected reflects informed professional judgment and practical understanding of green logistics practices in the local automotive sector. This sampling strategy strengthened the relevance and reliability of the dataset, providing a sound empirical basis for examining the relationships among green logistics practices and company performance.

In summary, the consensus approach ensures that eligible managers are included, providing comprehensive coverage of the population, while purposive sampling guarantees that participants have sufficient expertise and experience to contribute reliable insights into organizational operations, strategic planning, and leadership practices (Rahadian, 2022). This combined approach ensures that the study collects high-quality, context-specific data, thereby strengthening the internal validity and enhancing the applicability of the findings to the local automotive industry context.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents based on their Occupation and Years of Experience*

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Occupation	Manager	5	83.3%
	Officer-in-Charge	1	16.7%
Years of Experience	1-2 years	1	16.7%
	3-5 years	0	0%
	6-10 years	2	33.3%

10+ years	3	50.0%
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Table 2. *Level of Awareness of Green Logistics Practices*

Practice	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Reverse Logistics	3.00	0.63	Aware
Sustainable Use of Components	3.17	0.75	Aware
Route Optimization	3.17	0.41	Aware
Localized Eco-Friendly Sourcing	3.00	0.63	Aware
Optimized Space Allocation	3.17	0.41	Aware

Table 3. *Utilization of Green Logistics Practices*

Practice	Yes	No
Reverse Logistics	6 (100%)	0 (0%)
Sustainable Use of Components	6 (100%)	0 (0%)
Route Optimization	6 (100%)	0 (0%)
Localized Eco-Friendly Sourcing	5 (83.33%)	1 (16.67%)
Optimized Space Allocation	6 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 4. *Impact of Reverse Logistics on Supply Chain Efficiency*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Reverse Logistics	3.07	0.46	High Impact

Table 5. *Impact of Sustainable Use of Components on Supply Chain Efficiency*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sustainable Use of Components	3.20	0.40	High Impact

Table 6. *Impact of Route Optimization on Supply Chain Efficiency*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Route Optimization	3.24	0.33	High Impact

Table 7. *Impact of Localized Eco-Friendly Sourcing on Supply Chain Efficiency*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Localized Eco-Friendly Sourcing	3.23	0.37	High Impact

Table 8. *Impact of Optimized Space Allocation on Supply Chain Efficiency*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Optimized Space Allocation	3.13	0.42	High Impact

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Demographic Profile

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents based on their occupation and years of experience. Out of 6 respondents, 5 (83.3%) are managers, while 1 respondent (16.7%) is an officer-in-charge. Regarding the years of experience, 3 of the respondents (50.0%) have more than 10 years of experience, 2 respondents (33.3%) have around 6-10 years of experience, 1 respondent (16.7%) has 1-2 years of experience, while none have 3-5 years of experience.

The data indicates that the respondents hold substantial knowledge regarding the operations of their respective companies. As evidenced by their years of experience, their competence and business acumen allows them to provide educated and well-informed responses to the questions posed by the researchers. This implies that the responses came from well-equipped individuals who've utilized their years of experience to contribute to the study.

Level of Awareness of Green Logistics Practices

Table 2 shows the level of awareness of the respondents regarding the green logistics practices. Based on the data above, all of the respondents are aware of the green logistics practices, with minimal variability between the responses. Sustainable use of components, route optimization, and optimized space allocation received the highest level of awareness, with a mean score of 3.17 each.

The results illustrate that the respondents were aware of the green logistics practices mentioned in the study. The prevalence of such practices are noted within Valenzuela City, as evidenced by the data above. Optimized space allocation, sustainable use of components, and route optimization recorded the highest awareness levels (3.17). With a standard deviation of the practices ranging from 0.41 to 0.75, it implies that the data is close to the mean, which suggests a consistent response within the data gathered.

Utilization of Green Logistics Practices

Table 3 clarifies the utilization of green logistics practices within the automotive companies. The practices of reverse logistics, sustainable use of components, route optimization, and optimized space allocation are utilized by all 6 of the respondents within their respective companies (100%). Localized eco-friendly sourcing is utilized by 5 respondents (83.33%), with 1 respondent not utilizing such practice (16.67%).

The results show that, indeed, there is significant adoption of green logistics practices among the automotive firms in Valenzuela City, based on questionnaire responses regarding the extent to which reverse logistics, sustainable component usage, route optimization, localized eco-friendly sourcing, and optimized space utilization are implemented. These results support the findings of Hernandez et al. (2022), who identified that Philippine automotive and SME firms also consciously incorporate green logistics into their operational strategies. In light of the Resource-Based View, Barney (1991) would explain these practices as valuable organizational resources that strengthen efficiency and cannot easily be imitated by rivals.

Impact of Reverse Logistics on Supply Chain Efficiency

Table 4 shows the impact of reverse logistics on supply chain efficiency. Reverse logistics has a high impact on supply chain efficiency, with a mean score of 3.07, and a standard deviation of 0.46. It shows that the respondents generally agree on the positive contribution of the reverse logistics practices to operational efficiency. The relatively low standard deviation must be consistent in the responses.

The results support a positive relationship between reverse logistics and supply chain efficiency, with high impact on measurement items referring to operational performance, value recovery, flexibility, and long-term efficiency. It was observed that the general view of the respondents is that reverse logistics enhances operational performance, reinforces value recovery, and aids in greater supply chain flexibility when reinforced by new technologies. This confirms the first hypothesis posed by the researchers. In

addition, these findings confirm the results of Abbas and Tong (2023), Hernandez et al. (2022), and Reynolds (2024), who identified reverse logistics as the major driver for cost recovery, reduction of waste, and supply chain resilience in automotive firms. According to the Resource Dependency Theory, reverse logistics requires coordination in its activities with suppliers and customers so that it can enable firms to make better use of resources and enhance their efficiency on the whole. As evidenced by both empirical answers and existing literature, it can be stated that reverse logistics significantly contributes to improved supply chain efficiency. The companies may invest in advanced technologies and standardized processes for reverse logistics to further improve efficiency, flexibility, and long-term supply chain resilience.

Impact of Sustainable Use of Components on Supply Chain Efficiency

Table 5 presents the impact of sustainable use of components on supply chain efficiency. The results show a mean score of 3.20 with a standard deviation of 0.40, which is interpreted as having a high impact. This indicates that respondents consistently perceive sustainable component usage as a significant driver of efficiency.

The relatively high mean reflects strong agreement that adopting sustainable practices such as reducing waste, reusing materials, and prioritizing eco-friendly inputs enhances operational performance. These practices streamline processes, lower operational costs and production and distribution operations more consistently. This serves to integrate sustainability into every aspect of the supply chain, from procurement to distribution, and ensure that environmental considerations are embedded in decision-making processes (Hariyani, D. et al., 2024). The results also suggest that sustainability promotes better inventory management, more reliable sourcing, and lastly, fewer supply chain interruptions. Moreover, it supports the second hypothesis that there is a significant and positive relationship between the sustainable use of components and supply chain efficiency, demonstrating that sustainability is not only an environmental responsibility but also a strategic driver of operational and logistical effectiveness.

Impact of Route Optimization on Supply Chain Efficiency

Table 6 shows the impact of route optimization on supply chain efficiency. The mean score of 3.24 indicates the high impact of the practice, where respondents agree that route optimization improves efficiency-related outcomes such as time delivery, reduced transportation costs, and better resource utilization. The corresponding low standard deviation $SD = 0.33$ indicates that the respondents' perceptions are consistent, with little variation in their responses.

The findings imply that route optimization is recognized as an important strategy for enhancing supply chain efficiency. Route optimization has a positive effect on supply chain efficiency. The data suggests that planning and selecting the best delivery routes helps ensure faster and more reliable deliveries, lowers transportation costs, and makes better use of resources such as vehicles, fuel, and manpower. The data is in line with previous studies such as Abbas and Tong (2023). Furthermore, route optimization has been found to directly affect productivity and cost control in actual business operations. Businesses may limit vehicle wear and tear, save fuel consumption, and save total transportation costs by designing the most effective delivery routes. Moreover, it also helps ensure that products are delivered on time, improving customer satisfaction and reliability. Efficient routing allows better allocation of labor and vehicles, reducing idle time and increasing productivity. Overall, route optimization translates into measurable operational, financial, and strategic benefits for companies. This confirms the third hypothesis posed by the researchers.

Impact of Localized Eco-Friendly Sourcing on Supply Chain Efficiency

Table 7 illustrates the impact of localized eco-friendly sourcing on supply chain efficiency. The mean score of 3.23 represents the average response of the participants regarding localized eco-friendly sourcing. The standard deviation of 0.37 shows that the responses were closely clustered around the mean. This indicates a low level of variation among the participants' answers localized eco-friendly sourcing is

associated with a high level of impact, as respondents consistently rated it toward the higher end of the scale.

The findings imply that localized eco-friendly sourcing can have a beneficial effect on minimizing costs, lead time, and coordination within the supply chain. This consensus on the effectiveness of localized eco-friendly sourcing is supported by prior studies conducted by Hernandez et al. (2022) and Abbas and Tong (2023). Additionally, the advantages identified are replicable in real-life business operations as well. In practical business operations, the findings assume significance because they identify that through increased investments in localized eco-friendly sourcing practices, business entities can increase overall business efficiencies. Businesses can make use of these findings to substantiate their investments in forming localized connections with suppliers, minimizing their reliance on transporting products, and strengthening their eco-friendly operations without compromising supply chain performance. Such results support the fourth hypothesis posed by the researchers.

Impact of Optimized Space Allocation on Supply Chain Efficiency

Table 8 presents the impact of optimized space allocation on supply chain efficiency. The results show that optimized space allocation significantly affects supply chain efficiency. The mean score of 3.13 indicates that respondents generally agreed on its contribution to efficiency. The standard deviation of 0.42 suggests that the responses were relatively consistent among participants.

The findings imply that efficient space allocation enhances the efficiency of the supply chain by ensuring that everything that takes place within the business premises is well organized. This aligns with the findings by Hernandez et al. (2022) that effective space allocation enables the reduction of storages, enhances the accessibility of the products, enables faster processing of orders, and supports flexibility when dealing with changes in market demands. Through this, businesses can apply effective space allocation to optimize their storage capacity, eliminate business delays, enhance business efficiencies, and optimize business investments. This confirms the fifth hypothesis posed by the researchers.

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to identify the true impact of sustainable practices on the efficiency of automotive supply chains located in Valenzuela City. To be specific, it attempted to investigate the impact of 5 green logistics practices—reverse logistics, sustainable use of components, route optimization, localized eco-friendly sourcing, and optimized space allocation—on supply chain efficiency. The researchers hoped the paper would offer valuable insights on green logistics and equip decision-makers with the data necessary in order to improve current operations.

The findings state that each of the aforementioned green logistics practices have a significant impact on supply chain efficiency, answering the research questions posed by the researchers. Firstly, the practice of reverse logistics improves the firm's long-term execution of core activities and results in more flexibility, which is consistent with previous studies. Furthermore, the strategy helps refine future products, further boosting efficiency. Secondly, the practice of sustainable use of components reduces procurement costs and strengthens collaboration with suppliers, which agrees with previous studies. In addition, it helps the firm achieve long-term cost savings. Thirdly, the practice of route optimization reduces fuel usage through better navigation and reduces the firm's carbon footprint, which aligns with previous studies. Furthermore, it increases customer satisfaction levels and reduces the firm's operating costs. Fourthly, the practice of localized eco-friendly sourcing helps the firm maintain supplier relationships and improve stock replenishment rates, which affirms previous studies. Moreover, it results in higher inventory turnover rates and helps the firm manage inventory levels. Lastly, the practice of optimized space allocation improves order fulfillment procedures through more accessible and organized products, which is in line with previous research. Furthermore, proper space allocation improves space management, improves inventory

distribution, and allows the firm to adjust to stock differences quickly. In summary, each strategy was found to bring significant benefits to the productivity of the firm's value chain.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend that automotive companies utilize the paper as a foundation to improve green logistics and make it a best practice by incorporating reverse logistics, route optimization, sustainable use of parts, localized environmentally responsible sourcing, and space optimization into their logistics strategies. Companies are encouraged to invest in logistics technology such as route optimization software and inventory management software to reduce fuel consumption, minimize delivery times, and mitigate warehousing problems. Partnerships with local environmentally responsible suppliers are also encouraged to reduce transportation costs and emissions, as well as improve supply chain reliability.

In addition, the researchers recommend managers to promote green logistics projects by expressing sustainability goals in operational terms. This involves training employees on how to properly implement reverse logistics, sustainable material handling, and efficient warehouse design. Managers are encouraged to measure their performance on delivery time, inventory turnover, and cost savings to assess the success of green logistics practices. Moreover, managers are encouraged to facilitate cooperation between suppliers and logistics companies to promote the adoption of environmentally responsible and efficiency focused practices throughout the supply chain.

For future researchers, the researchers recommend extending current research by increasing the sample size and including more automotive companies from other cities or regions to improve generalizability. Long term research can be conducted to evaluate the long run effects of green logistics practices on supply chain efficiency and company performance. Moreover, future studies can combine qualitative research or explore moderating variables such as technology readiness, company size, or government support to gain more insights into the challenges and enablers of green logistics implementation in the Philippine automotive industry.

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